

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The practical significance of the research results, the conclusion obtained on the basis of theoretical knowledge about the ways, principles, criteria, mechanism for preparing long-term plans and programs related to the field of digital technologies in the system of distance education of specialists in the field of digital technologies. agricultural business and e-commerce in our republic, from the theoretical knowledge of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the area is explained by the fact that it can be used in the creation of educational programs, educational and methodological complexes, texts of lectures, teaching aids and textbooks in the education system khokimiyats, higher educational institutions.*

Keywords: *e-commerce, agrar business, training, platform, distance learning, specialist.*

Introduction

The implementation of new technologies in distance education and special attention to the potential of personnel determine the possibility of integrating management, innovation and digitalization of production. However, as a result of the influence of objective and subjective factors at various levels, the global Covid-19 pandemic and the widespread economic crises around the world lead to a number of controversial situations in the development of the industry. , that is, problematic situations in the development of distance education in the state, local governments, higher educational institutions and organizations. Therefore, the introduction of a differentiated digitalization system in developed countries with a modern system lays the foundation for distance learning of local business representatives and the use of this method, development of the system, application of modern technologies, and elimination of existing problems. and implementation of a modern digital system.

Along with the introduction of new digital technologies into the economy, the process of digitalization of public administration continues in world politics. The implementation of this process evenly depends on the level of each country, and the digitalization of public administration sets a high level. Digitalization of distance education includes several stages, as well as the creation of an effective system in the future, as well as a number of changes in the education system, the creation of a promising business time management system, and the functioning of a digitalization system for distance education. distance learning.

The development of the new century shows that the development of science depends on the system of digitalization of education, the progress of science is the growing demand for modern technologies, and every area needs young, capable professionals in their field. Also, an important issue today remains the solution of problems associated with the digitalization of distance education for specialists in the field of agricultural business and e-commerce and the creation of a systemic mechanism for them. Digitalization of distance education for specialists in the field of

agricultural business and e-commerce requires a number of scientific and practical works in order to determine the relationship between personnel, the labor market and manufacturers and establish smooth integration between them.

In recent years, reforms have been implemented in all areas of our republic, with special attention being paid to creating an effective and compact system. We will be able to see that this experience of accelerating the digital economy has produced positive results in developed countries. Digitalization of educational processes requires, first of all, the modernization of the organization's material and technical support. Therefore, the government is implementing a number of measures to further improve the efficiency of the education system in our republic.

The volume of market services provided in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021-2022 is 49 billion 111.0 billion dollars. increased to 253 billion 840.0 billion soums. compared to 2021 (119.5%), the growth rate was 115.4%.

It is necessary to take into account each process of digitalization of distance educational activities of specialists in the field of agricultural business and e-commerce, and to fully ensure information security, it is necessary to determine the following main directions:

Firstly: full implementation of e-commerce in the digitalization of educational activities, ensuring the business system at the national and international level;

secondly: be able to predict the main problems arising in education, as well as develop timely preventive measures and measures to minimize the consequences of problems;

thirdly: in order to integrate the creation of e-commerce services, radically reform the activities of distance education at different levels of society, minimize the development of services among the population.

Controlling every process and digitizing learning mechanisms is the main issue today, and at the same time, the main criterion is the formation of a competitive environment in the distance learning of specialists in the field of agricultural business and e-commerce. It should be recognized as necessary to develop the digital economy simultaneously with the introduction of a digitalization system for a radical reform of distance education for specialists in the field of agricultural business and e-commerce.

Therefore, it is natural that today the development of the digital economy, as well as the digitalization of distance education, will create a number of difficulties for the population and the state, because the main reason is the transition to a new system and the connection of several factors.

For determining the prospects for digitalization of the organization of distance learning and achieve a clear goal in the system, it is necessary to define the following tasks:

- based on the potential of each region, development of regional theoretical foundations for business digitalization;

- identify the main problems of organizing and managing the digitalization process taking into account national values and analyze its implementation;

- consideration of prospects for improving the system of distance education for specialists in the field of agricultural business and e-commerce and digitalization as an example of mutual cooperation between e-commerce and business;

At present time the systematization of distance education activities for specialists in the field of agricultural business and e-commerce based on digital technologies is a new stage not only in our country, but throughout the world, which indicates its preservation.

The introduction of distance education in the field of digital technologies in a manner compatible with the modern world, and the delivery of qualified personnel to the local labor market creates a number of the following problems (Fig. 1).

Particular problems arise while implementing any system and determining its effectiveness in the production process. Therefore, during the implementation of the system, it will be necessary to pay special attention to improving the qualifications of personnel.

Figure 1. Main problems awaiting solutions in the digitalization of distance education

From the above problem situations, it can be concluded that measures to remove each obstacle should be considered using a scientific approach.

The analysis of scientific approaches and their implementation in practice acquires particular importance in the context of digitalization of distance education activities.

At this stage, it is necessary to pay attention to the following main directions of digitalization of distance education activities:

ensuring constant informing of the international community about the activities of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, reforms implemented in its socio-political and socio-economic life, by providing relevant information resources in the field of distance education and the introduction of necessary technologies;

creating the necessary conditions for increasing the efficiency of mutual cooperation with legal entities and individuals in the digitalization of the activities of business representatives and government bodies in the field of distance education;

supporting the improvement of the quality and efficiency of distance education activities, taking into account the speed of information storage, printing and dissemination, as well as the level of business and e-commerce awareness in managing distance education activities;

distance learning in the process of digitalization and provision of information about the activities of organizations;

ensuring the participation of citizens in business management through participation in public discussion of regulatory legal documents, in the digitalization of distance learning, etc.

If the problems that may arise in the process of digitalization aren't analysed, while organizing distance education activities, this will directly affect the quality of work. For this reason, a number of scientists have explained the origin of conflicts in distance education activities and ways to eliminate them.

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